

AMIR TEMUR AS THE FOUNDER OF THE SECOND RENAISSANCE – THE TIMURID RENAISSANCE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19177526>

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada Amir Temurning davlat boshqaruvi, harbiy strategiyasi hamda ilm-fan, madaniyat va bunyodkorlik sohalaridagi faoliyati tahlil qilinadi. Sohibqiron tomonidan barpo etilgan markazlashgan qudratli davlat temuriylar davrida yuzaga kelgan Ikkinchi Uyg'onish davri — Temuriylar renessansining shakllanishiga mustahkam zamin yaratgani asoslab beriladi. Shuningdek, Temuriylar davrida ilm-fan, me'morchilik, adabiyot va san'atning yuksalishi Amir Temur siyosatining mantiqiy davomi ekani tarixiy manbalar asosida yoritiladi. Maqolada Amir Temurning bunyodkorlik faoliyati va uning jahon sivilizatsiyasi taraqqiyotidagi o'rni ilmiy jihatdan baholanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Amir Temur, Ikkinchi Uyg'onish davri, Temuriylar renessansi, markazlashgan davlat, bunyodkorlik, ilm-fan taraqqiyoti, madaniy meros, me'morchilik, davlat boshqaruvi, harbiy strategiya.

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируется государственная деятельность Амира Темура, его военная стратегия, а также вклад в развитие науки, культуры и созидательной деятельности. Обосновывается, что созданное Сахибкираном мощное централизованное государство стало прочной основой для формирования Второго Возрождения — Ренессанса эпохи Тимуридов. Освещается расцвет науки, архитектуры, литературы и искусства в период правления Тимуридов как закономерное продолжение политики Амира Темура. В статье даётся научная оценка созидательной деятельности Амира Темура и его роли в развитии мировой цивилизации.

Ключевые слова: Амир Темура, Второе Возрождение, Ренессанс Тимуридов, централизованное государство, созидательная деятельность, развитие науки, культурное наследие, архитектура, государственное управление, военная стратегия.

Abstract. This article analyzes the statecraft of Amir Temur, his military strategy, and his significant contributions to the development of science, culture, and creative construction. It substantiates that the powerful centralized state founded by Sahibqiran laid a solid foundation for the emergence of the Second Renaissance — the Timurid Renaissance. The flourishing of science, architecture, literature, and arts during the Timurid period is highlighted as a logical continuation of Amir Temur's policies. The article also provides a scholarly assessment of Amir Temur's constructive activities and his role in the advancement of world civilization.

Keywords: Amir Temur, Second Renaissance, Timurid Renaissance, centralized state, constructive activity, development of science, cultural heritage, architecture, state governance, military strategy.

Introduction

The personality of Amir Temur and his historical legacy occupy a special place in the history of Uzbekistan and world civilization. In the second half of the 14th century, the centralized and powerful state established by Sahibqiran not only ensured political stability but

also created broad opportunities for the development of science, culture, architecture, and art. It was precisely this strong political and social foundation that laid the groundwork for the formation of the Second Renaissance of the Timurid era — the Timurid Renaissance [4, p.23]. During the years of independence, the study of Amir Temur’s legacy was elevated to the level of state policy. In particular, on the basis of Resolution No. 630 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 29, 1994, the 660th anniversary of Sahibqiran’s birth was widely celebrated, and extensive work was carried out to deeply research and promote his historical services. This created the necessity to study Amir Temur’s activity on the basis of a new scientific approach [1, p.5].

This article analyzes Amir Temur’s system of state governance, his constructive policy, and his contribution to the development of science and culture, revealing his historical role as the founder of the Timurid Renaissance [6, p.15]. Amir Temur established a strong centralized state within a short period in the territory of Movarounnahr, which had fallen into fragmentation. He pursued a policy based on strict discipline, military strategy, and principles of just governance. In state administration, strict hierarchy, clear distribution of authority, loyalty, and discipline became the main criteria [4, p.26]. The governance system developed by Sahibqiran ensured economic stability in the country. Trade routes were restored, crafts and agriculture developed, and urban planning was implemented on a large scale. In particular, the revitalization of the Great Silk Road served to strengthen international trade and economic relations [8, p.57].

During Temur’s reign, the supremacy of law and the principle of justice acquired special significance. In the work known as *Temur Tuzuklari*, the system of state governance, military discipline, social relations, and moral values found expression. This formed the theoretical and practical foundation for building a strong state [3, p.118]. As a constructive ruler, Amir Temur also left a deep mark in history. During his reign, Samarkand became not only the capital of the empire but also a center of science and culture. Urban architecture reached a high level; grand mosques, madrasas, mausoleums, and palaces were constructed [5, p.70].

Temur attracted scholars, craftsmen, architects, and artists from various countries to his empire. This contributed to the formation of a scientific and cultural environment. His constructive policy was not limited to architecture but was also aimed at strengthening the spiritual atmosphere [7, p.6]. It was precisely this scientific and cultural environment that later flourished even more during the reign of the Timurid rulers. The observatory of Ulugh Beg, the Timurid literary school, the art of miniature painting, and the traditions of historiography became the logical continuation of the policy initiated by Amir Temur [6, p.19].

The Timurid period entered history as a new stage of the Eastern Renaissance. Significant achievements were made in science, particularly in astronomy, mathematics, historiography, literature, and art. The emergence of such outstanding examples as the scientific school of Ulugh Beg, the works of Alisher Navoi, and the art of Kamoliddin Behzod was not accidental [9, p.91]. The main characteristic of the Second Renaissance was the support of science and culture at the level of state policy, the high respect for scholars, and the creation of a favorable environment for creators. This process was closely connected with the political stability and centralized governance system established by Amir Temur [6, p.16]. Therefore, the Timurid Renaissance can be evaluated as the logical result of the school of statehood founded by Amir Temur. The political and spiritual foundation he created was continued at a high level by subsequent generations [9, p.96].

Today, the legacy of Amir Temur is recognized as an important spiritual foundation in the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan. His experience of statehood, governance principles based on justice and order, and attention to science are being interpreted in harmony with modern reforms [4, p.31]. As of 2025, scientific research on the Timurid period continues to expand. Archaeological research, the study of manuscripts, restoration and digitization of historical monuments are accelerating. Within the framework of international scientific cooperation, the Timurid Renaissance is being comparatively studied alongside the global Renaissance [10, p.538]. The formation of Amir Temur’s image in the minds of youth as a symbol of patriotism, dedication, and constructive leadership is considered one of the priority directions of today’s spiritual and educational policy [4, p.23].

Conclusion. The centralized state established by Amir Temur became the main factor in the Second Renaissance process of the Timurid era. His wise governance, strong military strategy, and large-scale constructive policy created a solid foundation for the flourishing of science and culture. The Timurid Renaissance emerged as the logical result of the political stability and spiritual environment founded by Amir Temur. The rise of science, architecture, literature, and art represents the continuation of the path of development initiated by Sahibqiran.

Recommendations. 1. It is necessary to expand source studies and archaeological research on the Timurid period.

2. Manuscript sources should be digitized and introduced into international academic circulation.

3. It is advisable to introduce special courses on Timurid statehood into the higher education system.

4. Scientific and spiritual projects promoting Amir Temur’s legacy among youth should be strengthened.

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